

VACUUM ASSISTED TECHNIQUES FOR IMPROVED REPAIR PERFORMANCE IN LEGACY FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Some large fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) marine structures—such as the U.K.’s mine countermeasures vessels—were designed decades ago. Of these early designs, some entered production, and have been in regular service for many years. When compared to modern FRP structures, the sparsity of literature available for legacy structures means they often constitute an asset maintenance dilemma. In these contexts, certain repair variables are often fixed according to the original design and are not possible to change easily. Examples could include the materials used in the repair and laminate structure. This paper presents a study aimed at improving the effectiveness of repairs on these legacy marine FRPs by using vacuum assistance to produce higher quality repairs, without changing the materials used in, or the design of, the repairs. First, the relationship between consolidation pressure applied to a wet lay-up repair and the repair’s performance, was investigated. Thereafter, a vacuum-assisted resin infusion process replaced the wet lay-up, to demonstrate further improvements in repair performance. Both of these improvements are based on the repair procedures, and are readily implementable within the asset maintenance programs of in-service legacy marine FRP structures. Extending the life of these structures by means of improved repair practices like these would mitigate their environmental impact by reducing unnecessary structure downtime and premature decommissioning, especially where end-of-life disposal processes are limited and environmentally harmful.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre Reinforced Polymer (FRP) composites have been widely adopted across a range of applications, with marine structures among the earliest large-scale implementations. Notably, the United Kingdom’s mine countermeasures vessels (MCMVs), introduced in the latter half of the twentieth century, represent significant examples of early FRP structural use. These vessels—many of which remain in service—pose a number of challenges with respect to maintenance. For example, the original materials and lay-up configurations are typically fixed, limiting how current repair techniques may be enhanced or adapted.

The broader field of FRP repair has advanced considerably in recent decades, particularly with respect to aerospace applications, where the drive for high performance has led to increasingly sophisticated repair methodologies [1]. Within the marine domain, however, repairs are often carried out under less controlled conditions, and the dominant technique—manual wet lay-up—remains heavily dependent on operator experience. This introduces variability in the quality of repairs, particularly in relation to void content, resin distribution, and fibre alignment, all of which can significantly influence structural performance [2]. In the context of legacy marine composites, there remains a clear need for repair strategies that are both robust and compatible with existing material systems.

Scarf repair continues to be the preferred method for repairing damage on composite structures in the marine industry, primarily due to its capacity to recover in-plane load-bearing capacity when appropriately executed [3]. There are a number of different factors that affect the quality of scarf repair,

and in the following section brief accounts of parameters such as taper angle, surface preparation, and ply sequencing are provided.

The scarf or taper angle θ_{sc} is defined as the angle between the surface of the repaired laminate and the inclined plane of the bond line formed between the original material and the repair patch. Mathematically, the scarf angle is expressed in degrees, though it is commonly referenced via the taper ratio—defined as the length of the taper divided by the thickness of the laminate. Composite repair handbooks often recommend a tapered slope between 20:1 and 50:1 [4][5] although practically on ships this is not always possible and ratios of 12:1 are considered acceptable with $\theta_{sc} < 5^\circ$ [3]. Optimisation studies on how taper angle affects peak stresses on 8 ply thick fibre composite, have been done by Bendemra and Compston [8], with taper angles ranging from 3° to 12° . They found peak stresses increased exponentially with scarf angle, with a greater stress increase from a scarf angle of going from 8° to 12° than with an increase from 3° to 5° . A study by Ahn and Springer [5] found that increasing the scarf angle from 0.5° to 2.5° decreased the failure load although only minimally concluding scarf angle becomes increasingly relevant at larger taper angles.

To ensure a good quality bond between the old fibres and the new, surface contaminants should be reduced to a minimum. This is recommended to be achieved with the use of a solvent, often acetone [3]. Sanding is recommended to roughen up the surface abrading it and improving bond strength. Ahn and Springer [5] tested how failure load varies on a scarf repair with different grit numbers on a diamond sander. It was found that changing the grit number had a negligible effect on failure load concluding that a grit of 100 would be reasonable for scarf repair.

There are two ply sequencing techniques used in scarf repair. The first technique is to lay the smallest patch down first and increase in size towards the repair surface. The second is to start with the largest patch and decrease in size. Among marine FRP operators, The National Maritime Centre, have reported the former method produces a relatively weak resin rich layer at the surface of the repair and recommend the latter technique of placing the largest ply first [6]. Additionally, the former technique has been reported to produce weaker points of increased stress at the end of each ply, where cracks would often propagate from [3].

Adding additional layers of laminate to the repair surface, overlapping at the edge of the repair to bond to the original material has been found by Ahn and Springer [5] to increase failure load, for example, the addition of two external plies increased failure load by approximately 50%. Similar results were reported by Myhre and Beck [7]. Research into the effect of the over-ply lap length (i.e., how far the external ply extends over the repair region) was done by Bendemra and Compston [8], concluding that peak peel stress was significantly reduced by inclusion of over-ply, and identifying a critical lap length of 5 mm.

Recent work has highlighted the potential for process-level improvements—rather than material substitution—to deliver tangible gains in repair quality. In particular, vacuum-assisted techniques have shown promise in improving consolidation and reducing void formation in manually applied repairs. These approaches are especially attractive in the context of legacy FRP structures, where the scope for altering material or geometric parameters is limited.

This paper presents an investigation into the potential for improving repair performance in legacy FRP marine structures by refining the repair process itself. The study first examines the influence of consolidation pressure in traditional wet lay-up repairs and subsequently explores the application of a vacuum-assisted resin infusion method. Both approaches were designed to be compatible with the constraints typical of legacy vessel maintenance, requiring no change to material systems or laminate design. The findings contribute to ongoing efforts to support the long-term serviceability of FRP marine assets, while aligning with broader objectives around sustainability and responsible lifecycle management in composite structures.

2 METHODOLOGIES

2.1 Manufacturing original laminates

The material system and manufacturing methods were selected to represent that of typical marine composite structures. Crystic 701PAX isophthalic polyester resin and (2% by volume) Butanox M50 methyl ethyl ketone peroxide crosslinking initiator, were combined and subsequently impregnated by

hand into the reinforcing fibres. The reinforcement was Scott & Fyfe “Polyform WR” 800 g m⁻² plain woven glass mat. For all original (reference and pre-repair) laminates the lay-up recipe was [0₈]_T. The curing cycle was 24 h at room temperature (20°C) in a closed mould process with no additional environmental control or post-curing steps.

2.2 Scarf repair design

To evaluate different repair methods, a single-sided surface-to-midplane scarf repair was designed (Fig. 1). This simulates a typical repair process that is often followed for damage that extends not further than the laminate midplane. For this type of damage, the repair is usually conducted exclusively from one side of the structure. Herein, material was removed from one surface of the laminate in a stepped pattern until the laminate midplane was reached. Thereafter, the stepped patterns were graded to create scarf angles of 5°. Dry fibre plies of the same reinforcement were cut to match the quantity and dimensions of the removed plies. These repair plies were laid up monolithically according to the direction of the parent laminate. For wet lay-up cases, the repair plies were impregnated by hand using brushes and rollers, in a ply-by-ply manner. For vacuum infusion methods, repair plies were laid up dry, and resin injected into the scarf repair zone using the parent laminate as a mould base. In all cases, one additional surface ply was applied with over-ply areas bonded to the surface of the original laminate on each side of the repair.

Figure. 1: Ply arrangement in laminate repair patch.

2.3 Improved repair part 1: consolidation pressure

In initial investigations, repair plies were exclusively impregnated by manual wet lay-up. Four original laminates were manufactured according to Section 2.1: one reference laminate and four test case laminates. The test case laminates were scarfed and repaired according to Section 2.2. All scarf repairs were cured for 24 h at room temperature (20°C) in a closed-mould process using a Radius 70T platen press machine with no additional environmental control or post-curing steps. To investigate the influence of pressure applied during consolidation, each scarf repair was cured at a unique value of consolidation pressure. The four values of consolidation pressure were 0 kPa, 100 kPa, 300 kPa, and 600 kPa.

2.4 Improved repair part 2: impregnation method

In a subsequent investigation, repair plies were impregnated by two methods: 1) manual wet lay-up and 2) vacuum resin infusion. Two original laminates were manufactured according to Section 2.1. Both laminates were scarfed according to Section 2.3. The first laminate was repaired in a wet lay-up process at 1 bar of applied pressure, whilst the second laminate was repaired using vacuum resin infusion to wet out the repair plies. Both scarf repairs were cured for 24 h at room temperature (20°C) with no additional environmental control or post-curing steps.

2.5 Data acquisition

2.5.2 Flexure

Five specimens per case were tested in accordance with BS EN ISO 14125 [9]. Specimens were loaded in crosshead displacement-controlled flexure at a constant rate of 4.5 mm min⁻¹, using an Instron 3369 with a 10 kN load cell and Wyoming Test Fixtures Four-Point Flexure Test Fixture (Fig. 2a). An MTS AVX04 video extensometer package was used to capture specimen central displacement data at a sampling rate of 10.02 ± 0.02 Hz. Average specimen widths and thicknesses were calculated from vernier calliper measurements taken at three locations, before a speckle pattern was applied to the central

20 mm of the specimen side (through thickness) facing the camera. Specimens were placed centrally on the (5 mm diameter) support rollers with the loading axis being normal to the long edge of the specimen. Tests were concluded at ultimate failure of the specimens, defined as an instantaneous stress drop exceeding 50% of the preceding measured value.

The nominal flexural stress observed in the specimen outer surface at specimen mid-span, is denoted σ_f and is defined in Equation 1 where P is the load measured, L is the specimen span (defined in the standard as $(16.5 \times h)$), b is the specimen width, h is the specimen thickness. Flexural strain in the specimen outer surface at specimen mid-span, is denoted ε_f , and is defined in Equation 2 where: s is the deflection of the mid-span of the specimen under load, h is the specimen thickness, L is the specimen span (defined in the standard as $16.5h$). Flexural strength, σ_{fM} , is defined as the first local maximum flexural stress observed. Flexural modulus, E_f , is defined as the initial slope of the flexural stress-strain curve, for the region $0.05\% \leq \varepsilon_f \leq 0.25\%$ (Equation 3) where ΔF is the difference in loads corresponding to deflections s'' and s' , Δs is the difference in mid-span deflections (s'' and s') corresponding to flexural strains 0.25% and 0.05%, respectively.

$$\sigma_f = PL/bh^2 \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_f = 4.7sh/L^2 \quad (2)$$

$$E_f = \frac{0.21L^3}{bh^3} \left(\frac{\Delta F}{\Delta s} \right) \quad (3)$$

2.5.1 In-plane shear

Five specimens per case were tested in accordance with ASTM D3518 [10]. Specimens were loaded in crosshead displacement-controlled tension at a constant rate of 2 mm min^{-1} using an MTS Criterion C45.305 (Fig. 2b) fitted with a 250 kN load cell and hydraulic wedge grips. An MTS AVX04 video extensometer package was used to capture strain data at a sampling rate of $10.02 \pm 0.02 \text{ Hz}$. Average specimen widths and thicknesses were calculated from vernier calliper measurements taken at three locations, before a speckle pattern was applied to 50 mm of the central gauge region. Specimens were clamped in the crosshead grips with 100 kPa clamping pressure applied evenly to the entire grip region. The loading axis was parallel to the long edge of the $\pm 45^\circ$ specimen. Tests were concluded at ultimate failure of the specimens, defined as an instantaneous stress drop exceeding 90% of the preceding measured value.

In-plane shear stress observed within the gauge region—parallel to the xy plane—is denoted τ_{xy} , and is defined in Equation 4, where P_x is the load measured and A is the original specimen cross-sectional area, as measured before the test. Shear strain observed—in the direction of the loading axis—is denoted γ_{xy} , and is defined in Equation 5, where Δl_x is the linear displacement of two targeted observation zones within the specimen gauge region, l_x is the original linear separation of the two target observation zones, as measured before the test. In plane shear strength, τ_{xyM} , is defined as the shear stress observed at $\gamma_{xy} = 5.0\%$. In plane shear modulus—in the direction of the loading axis—, G_{xy} , is defined as the initial slope of the shear stress-strain curve, for the region $0.05\% \leq \gamma_{xy} \leq 0.25\%$ (Equation 6), where τ''_{xy} is the stress measured at $\gamma_{xy} = 0.25\%$, τ'_{xy} is the stress measured at $\gamma_{xy} = 0.05\%$, $\gamma'_{xy} = 0.05\%$, $\gamma''_{xy} = 0.25\%$.

$$\tau_{xy} = P_x/2A \quad (4)$$

$$\gamma_{xy} = \Delta l_x/l_x \quad (5)$$

$$G_{xy} = \frac{\tau''_{xy} - \tau'_{xy}}{\gamma''_{xy} - \gamma'_{xy}} \quad (6)$$

Figure. 2. Standardized experimental test setups: (a) flexure, (b) in-plane shear.

2.5.3 Density and fibre volume fraction

Density determination was completed using an Ohaus Adventurer AX324 analytical balance paired with an Ohaus density determination kit, which exploits Archimedes' principle by comparison of dry mass, A , to that observed when the specimen is submerged in a known liquid, B —shown in Equation 7, where ρ_c is the density of the specimen, ρ_0 is the density of the liquid—in this case, distilled water; 0.998 g cm^{-3} at 20°C —and ρ_L is the air density (0.0012 g cm^{-3}). For each test case, five extractions of approximately 100 mm^2 were cut from random locations in the respective plates using a diamond bladed wet saw. Specimen conditioning before and after submersion was completed in a Prolan environmental chamber in accordance with ISO 185 291:2008 [11]. FVFs, V_r were measured through a pyrolysis/burn-off approach—as specified in ASTM D3171-22 Method I [12]—using a Nabertherm L15/11 muffle furnace and Haldenwanger porcelain crucibles with lids. The expression shown in Equation 8 was used to calculate the FVF where M_r is the mass of reinforcement remaining in the crucible at completion of the pyrolysis. One additional crucible containing traveller fibres verified that fibre mass-loss through the pyrolysis process was negligible. The pyrolysis cycle was determined using thermal degradation data acquired from Thermogravimetric Analysis of the same cured isophthalic polyester resin (2% hardener). The pyrolysis cycle began with a chamber ramp rate of $10^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ from ambient temperature to a maximum temperature of 600°C . This maximum temperature was sustained for 6 hours to ensure full burn-off of all the resin in the samples. Thereafter, the furnace chamber underwent a passive cooldown to return to the ambient temperature.

$$\rho_c = \frac{A}{A - B} (\rho_0 - \rho_L) + \rho_L \quad (7)$$

$$V_r = 100 M_r \frac{\rho_c}{\rho_L} \quad (8)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Improved repair part 1: consolidation pressure

The flexural strengths of repaired specimens are plotted against repair consolidation pressure in Fig. 3a. Increased flexural strengths were observed for specimens with repairs cured under higher consolidation pressures. Non-linear fits were applied to the mean values from each set to infer the relationship between repair cure consolidation pressure and flexural strength within the empirical range. It is suggested that the presence of the scarf repair redistributes the internal stresses under load, and that the extra surface plies in the repair zones contributed to improved compression-under-flexure responses compared to the reference cases. Similar observations were drawn from the flexural stiffness data in Fig. 3b. Most repaired specimens exhibited higher flexural moduli compared to the reference specimens.

Figure 3: Flexural properties of repaired specimens vs. consolidation pressure: (a) strengths, (b) moduli.

Similarly, the in-plane shear strengths of repaired specimens were compared to their reference specimen counterparts in Fig. 4a. Again, increased consolidation pressures were correlated with increased in-plane shear performance. Similar observations can be made about the in-plane shear moduli in Fig. 4b, which increased marginally as a function of increased consolidation pressure. However, the standard deviations of each test case are large relative to the respective means. Consequently, it is suggested that a minimum threshold repair consolidation pressure is required to ensure appropriate

Figure 4: In-plane shear properties of repaired specimens vs. consolidation pressure: (a) strengths, (b) moduli.

bonding of the repair patch, however, once this threshold has been achieved, additional applied pressure may not significantly improve the in-plane shear properties of the repaired laminates. It is reasoned that since in-plane shear properties are dominated by interlaminar fracture, these damage mechanisms are not easy to treat with applied pressure alone. Furthermore, this scarf repair approach generated plies that were not in-plane with the applied load, and thereby, geometrical effects could have complicated the experimental data interpretation.

The influence of FVF on FRP mechanical properties is well documented, e.g., Refs [13-14], therefore this observation is intuitive. Higher consolidation pressures had the effect of increasing FVF through reductions in void content and increased expulsion of excess resin from the moulds. One method to control for fluctuations in FVFs, is to consider specific properties, i.e., properties divided by densities, on the basis that the specimen density implies information about the specimen volume fractions. Considering the specific flexural properties in Table 1, repairs consolidated under higher pressures performed better, implying that these improvements were not solely driven by enhanced FVFs.

Table 1: Mean specimen flexural properties as measured during part 1 of the study.

Category	$\bar{\rho}$ [g cm ⁻³]	\bar{V}_r [%]	\bar{E}_{fSP} [kNm kg ⁻¹]	$\bar{\sigma}_{fMSP}$ [kNm kg ⁻¹]
Ref.	1.72 ± 0.01	39.4 ± 0.4	9.14E+03 ± 179.1	126.3 ± 05.2
0	1.68 ± 0.01	36.4 ± 0.6	7.55E+03 ± 443.8	127.5 ± 17.1
1	1.68 ± 0.01	36.4 ± 0.5	9.86E+03 ± 397.9	152.5 ± 07.3
3	1.73 ± 0.01	40.3 ± 0.9	1.02E+04 ± 291.9	150.6 ± 06.2
6	1.74 ± 0.02	40.1 ± 1.4	1.06E+04 ± 292.3	156.3 ± 11.5

Similarly in Table 2, improvements in specific in-plane shear strengths are correlated with higher consolidation pressures. Since the repairs all fail at the repair line it follows that increased consolidation pressures would improve the quality of that repair bond through void reduction, thereby increasing the energy required to induce and propagate interlaminar cracks.

Table 2: Mean specimen in-plane shear properties as measured during part 1 of the study.

Category	$\bar{\rho}$ [g cm ⁻³]	\bar{V}_r [%]	\bar{G}_{12SP} [kNm kg ⁻¹]	$\bar{\tau}_{12 SP}$ [kNm kg ⁻¹]
Ref.	1.72 ± 0.01	39.4 ± 0.4	1161.3 ± 49.9	16.7 ± 0.5
0	1.68 ± 0.01	36.4 ± 0.6	648 ± 70.2	16.7 ± 0.3
1	1.68 ± 0.01	36.4 ± 0.5	1311.8 ± 53.5	17.3 ± 0.2
3	1.73 ± 0.01	40.3 ± 0.9	1217.0 ± 47.9	18.7 ± 0.3
6	1.74 ± 0.02	40.1 ± 1.4	1398.2 ± 65.6	19.2 ± 0.3

3.1 Improved repair part 2: impregnation method

Table 3 shows the mean flexural properties of the reference and repaired specimens. The reference specimens naturally showed the highest mean flexural strength, whilst wet lay-up repaired specimens were restored to 91.3% of the mean reference strength, and VARTM repaired specimens were restored to only 62.1% of the mean reference strength. Both repair methods resulted in consistent flexural moduli (20.0 - 21.3 GPa), indicating that the repair method mainly influenced strength rather than stiffness.

Table 4 shows the mean in-plane shear properties of the reference and repaired specimens. The reference specimens again showed highest mean shear strength, establishing a baseline for evaluating repair performance. The specimens repaired by wet lay-up were restored to 91.7% of reference shear strength and 69.5% of the reference shear modulus. The VARTM repaired specimens were restored to 83.9% of the reference shear strength 66.3% of the reference shear modulus. For both repair methods strength recovery was better than modulus recovery, indicating that whilst repair method changed the energy required to initiate and propagate failure, the resulting material had consistent elastic behaviour.

Table 3: Mean specimen flexural properties as measured during part 2 of the study.

Category	$\bar{\rho}$ [g cm ⁻³]	\bar{V}_r [%]	\bar{E}_f [GPa]	$\bar{\sigma}_{fM}$ [MPa]
Ref.	1.75 ± 0.01	39.8 ± 0.6	20.1 ± 1.2	327 ± 30.2
Wet Lay-up	1.74 ± 0.02	39.6 ± 2.0	21.3 ± 0.5	289 ± 15.3
VARTM	1.77 ± 0.03	39.3 ± 2.0	20.8 ± 1.6	212 ± 16.4

The mean specific flexural strengths (Fig. 5a) follow similar trends: the reference laminate achieved the highest specific strength, with 88% restoration of mean specific flexural strength for specimens repaired by wet lay-up and 64% restoration of mean specific flexural strength for specimens repaired by VARTM. Although a marginal increase can be seen in the mean specific flexural moduli of specimens repaired by wet lay-up compared to VARTM (Fig. 5b), there is considerable overlap of the datapoints after accounting for the standard deviations of each set. Further analysis via t-test revealed no statistical significance ($p > 0.05$) in the mean flexural moduli data.

Table 4: Mean specimen in-plane shear properties as measured during part 2 of the study.

Category	$\bar{\rho}$ [g cm ⁻³]	\bar{V}_r [%]	\bar{G}_{12} [GPa]	$\bar{\tau}_{12M}$ [MPa]
Ref.	1.75 ± 0.01	39.8 ± 0.6	4.0 ± 0.3	40.9 ± 3.7
Wet Lay-up	1.74 ± 0.02	39.6 ± 2.0	2.8 ± 0.2	37.5 ± 4.1
VARTM	1.77 ± 0.03	39.3 ± 2.0	2.7 ± 0.2	34.3 ± 3.4

Fig. 6a shows the mean specific in-plane shear strengths, which follow similar trends to their flexural strength counterparts. The wet lay-up repairs restored an average of 92% of the mean reference specific in-plane shear strength, whilst the VARTM repairs restored an average of 81% of the reference mean specific in-plane shear strength. For specific in-plane shear modulus (Fig. 6b), wet lay-up again out-performed VARTM in terms of performance restoration, however, neither method was able to match the specific in-plane shear modulus of the reference case. Despite the numerical differences between repair methods no statistical differences exists between repair methods for shear stress ($p = 0.078$) or modulus ($p=0.086$) indicating from a practical perspective, both methods offer statistically equivalent in-plane shear performance.

The similarities between flexural and in-plane shear performances in part 2 of this study implies that wet lay-up repairs out-perform VARTM repairs in terms of strength, whilst marginal difference can be detected in terms of stiffness.

Figure 5: Flexural properties of repaired specimens vs. manufacturing method:
 (a) strengths, (b) moduli.

Figure 6: In-plane shear properties of repaired specimens vs. manufacturing method: (a) strengths, (b) moduli.

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, repair strategies for legacy fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) marine composites, were investigated. Focus was given to process-driven improvements that do not require changes to material systems. Two approaches were considered: 1. Increasing consolidation pressure during wet lay-up repairs, and 2. Using vacuum-assisted resin infusion (VARTM) as an alternative impregnation method. Repairs cured under higher consolidation pressures resulted in increased flexural and in-plane shear strengths. These gains were partially attributed to higher fibre volume fractions, but improvements in specific strength properties indicated enhanced load transfer and bonding quality too. In the latter part of the study, VARTM repairs resulted in specimens with comparable flexural and in-plane shear strengths to the traditional wet lay-up method. Similarly, no statistically significant differences in flexural or in-plane shear stiffnesses, were detected. Overall, the findings indicate that both increased consolidation pressures and vacuum-driven impregnation methods have potential to improve the mechanical performance of repaired specimens. Beyond the structural performances, the optimization of these techniques can support broader sustainability goals (reducing unnecessary or premature disposal) by extending the useful lives of in-service assets.

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